

EXPLORING THE DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING SCIENCE AMONG INTERMEDIATE GRADE TEACHERS IN SELECTED SCHOOLS IN MBHTE SULU, SOUTHERN PHILIPPINES: BASIS FOR PROGRAM INTERVENTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed at determining the difficulties in teaching the learning contents in Science experienced by the selected elementary school teachers in Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education in Sulu, Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (MBHTE-Sulu), Southern Philippines this school year 2022-2023. Descriptive survey method was used to investigate the difficulties of teaching Science among intermediate grade teachers in selected schools in MBHTE-Sulu. The subjects of this study were the intermediate grade teachers coming from the 30 elementary schools. These teachers have different educational qualification, teaching experience, status of appointment, number of trainings. Meanwhile, Frequency counts and percentage, Mean, T-Test and ANOVA were used in the treatment of data. Results revealed that majority of the elementary school teachers of MBHTE-Sulu were female; belonging to 36-45 years of age ; with bachelors' degree and some were still pursuing their advance studies; and with 5-10 years teaching experience. Categorically, the teachers found that teaching the learning content in Biology, Physical Science and Earth and Space Science would be moderately difficult. Further, there could be no significant difference found between the perception of the teachers of MBHTE-Sulu in terms of difficulties in teaching the learning

contents in science with respect to their gender, age, educational qualifications and their teaching experiences. Moreover, there was no significant difference found on the difficulties in terms of selecting appropriate methods and strategies in teaching science according to Respondents' Profile.

Keywords: difficulties, teaching Science, interventions, teachers' demographic profile

INTRODUCTION

The goals of science teaching have undergone remarkable shifts, but the problem of improving the quality of science instruction remains. The most frustrating problems facing our society is the continuing pattern of low achievement prevalent in many schools, especially in science (Cortes, 2005).

It is believed that students' scientific competencies are at the nerve center of learning science learning contents. So to equip our students with the basic science literacy necessary in modern society, developing students' scientific competencies has become one of the most essential objectives of science education (DeBoer, 2000;, & Millar, 2006; Tsai, 2015).

This scenario also holds true in MBHTE-Sulu in the Bangsamoro Region in Muslim Mindanao, Southern Philippines where teachers in the intermediate grade level have also facing several challenges in the mainstream of classroom instruction. It is very hard for teachers to facilitate learning in the classroom considering the in-depth contents of science, the classroom strategies and materials to be used , more so, the way how students being evaluated in the light of the k-12 curriculum.

Chio (2010) Argued that unless science teacher is thoroughly knowledgeable of the subject matter, varies his/her lesson presentation, methods and techniques, uses a variety of instructional materials, and knows how to evaluate, yet pupils' achievement in the subject will not be improved. According to some science teachers, most of their pupils have low performance in science. Pupils' performance in any field and more particularly in science is believed to be greatly influenced by teacher preparation. Science teachers' preparation is now recognized as a pivotal point in the reform of science education (Adams, 2005). While Anderman and Sinatra (2021) argued that many of negative experiences associated with the learning of science in schools can be avoided if science educators are cognizant of both the cognitive abilities of all adolescent learners.

Furthermore, Filoteo (2018) mentioned in her research on "teachers lay the task of strengthening basic education through teaching and promotion of primary and secondary science to students", though the task not easy, teachers must know and keep a breast with content. They must familiar with a variety of methods, instructional materials, and more importantly, they must know and understand the nature of the learners.

Moreover, Metin (2013) found that teachers do not determine appropriate topics for students' level and appropriate criteria for topics and have insufficient knowledge about how prepared rubrics. Besides, it is seen that teachers encounter some difficulties such as crowded classroom, insufficient time for assessment, insufficient learning environment and technological opportunity and they do not do objective assessment.

On the basis of the above premises, the researchers were encouraged to conduct an investigation on the difficulties of teaching science in the selected schools in MBHTE-Sulu, Division of Sulu. This paper fervently hopes to draw some significant benefits to all educationists alike particularly to intermediate grade teachers, school administrators, and other stakeholders alike.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Generally, this study sought to explore the difficulties in teaching Science contents ; and the difficulties of utilizing appropriate methods and strategies by teachers in Pangutaran District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education, Division of Sulu, Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What are the demographic profile of the intermediate grade teachers teaching Science in terms of the following in the context of Age, Gender, Educational qualification, and Teaching experience?
2. What are the extent of difficulties encountered by the teachers in teaching Science in terms of (A) teaching the content areas and (B) in terms of teaching methods and strategies used?
3. Is there significant differences in the difficulties encountered in teaching science when the data are categorized according to the following in terms of Age, Educational qualification, and Teaching experience

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Pangutaran District in the Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE) Province of Sulu situated along the Southern Hemisphere of the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), Philippines. Pangutaran District is an Island district situated in the southern part of the Province of Sulu. The study comprised 30 elementary schools with 25 school principals; five officer's in-charge; and 180 faculty members.

Sampling Method

The researchers used total enumeration sampling to include all 180 elementary school teachers in the different elementary schools in Pangutaran District of Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education (MBHTE) in Sulu, Bangsamoro Autonomous Region and Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), Southern Philippines.

Meanwhile, the researchers have sought formal permission from the School Division Superintendent of Sulu for the launching of questionnaires to the respondents. Upon approval, the questionnaires were distributed to all the selected elementary Schools through their respective school administrators. . Further, the selected respondents answered the self-structured questionnaire to evaluate the difficulties of teaching science in the areas of content and methods or strategies. Completed questionnaires were

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retrieved by the teaching assistants and handed over to the researchers. The questionnaire administration and retrieval lasted for a month. All questionnaires distributed were retrieved with 100% response rate.

Research Instrument

A self-structured-questionnaire was used as a data-gathering tool. Some parts of the questionnaire were extracted from the review of related studies. While others were patterned from the work of Chino (2016) and Leo (20018). The legal basis in the formulation of instrument was derived from the K-12 curriculum of 2015, particularly with regard science.

The first part of the questionnaire contains the profile or personal background of the respondents. It includes gender, age, educational qualification, teaching experience, status of appointment and number of trainings attended. The second part of the questionnaire is composed of 20 items related to difficulties in teaching science contents. This includes seven (7) questions for learning contents in Biology; seven (7) questions for learning contents in Physical Science; and six (6) questions for learning contents in Earth and Space Science. Moreover, the last part of the questionnaire is a 15 items pertaining to methods and strategies used by teachers in teaching Science.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive and inferential statistical tools was appropriately employed in the treatment of data to be gathered for this study. Frequency counts and percentage was employed to determine the profile of employees of elementary teachers of MBHTE-Sulu; While, mean and standard deviation was employed to determine the extent of difficulties encountered by the teachers in teaching Science. Moreover, T-test was used to determine the significant difference according to gender; while ANOVA the significant difference in terms of age, educational qualification, and teaching experience.

Scope and Delimitation

This investigation attempts to determine the extent of difficulties in teaching science among intermediate grade teachers in selected school in Pangutaran District, Division of Sulu. This includes the profile of the respondents as identified in problem number one. The extent of difficulties encountered by the teachers in teaching Science is delimited to the following areas of instructions: a) teaching the content areas, b) using suitable teaching methods and strategies. Other areas in classrooms instruction like utilization of learning materials and evaluation of student progress are not included in this study.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings of the study align with its objectives. The first part analyzes the demographic profile of the respondents and the second part entails of the difficulties encountered by elementary school teachers in MBHTE-Sulu in terms of subject contents and in terms method and strategies. And the last part tackles the significant difference on the difficulties in terms of contents and in terms of methods and strategies according to demographic profile of the respondents.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the profile of the elementary school teacher in MBHTE-Sulu in terms of their gender, age, length of service and their educational qualification. As to gender, the majority (72.2%) of the elementary school teachers were female; as to age, majority(50 %) have an age bracket of 36-45 years old; As to their educational qualification, majority 110 (61.1%) have finished their bachelor's degree. And as to teaching experience, majority (44.4%) have already been in service from 5-10 years;

Table 1 : Profile of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Per cent
Male	50	27.8
Female	130	72.2
Age		
24-35 years old	49	27.5
36-45 years old	90	50.0
46-55 years old	30	16.7
56-65 years old	11	5.9
Educational Qualification		
Bachelor's Degree	110	61.1
With Master's Units	59	33.0
Master's Degree	11	5.9
With Doctoral Units	0	0.0
Doctoral Degree	0	0.0
Teaching Experience		
Below 5 years	60	33.3
5-10 years	80	44.4
Over 10 years	40	22.3

Difficulties in Teaching Learning Contents in Science

Table 2 provides the result of the difficulties in teaching the learning contents in science as rated by teachers themselves. The overall mean for the difficulties in teaching the learning contents was 2.74 . While the individual means are as follows : Learning content in Biology (mean = 2.59) ; Learning content in Physical Science (mean = 2.88) ; and Learning content in Environmental and Space Science (mean = 2.73)

Table 2 : Difficulties in Teaching the Learning Content in Science

Difficulties	Verbal Description
A. Learning Content in Biology	

1. Features distinguishing living from non-living systems.	2.06	Slightly Difficult
2. Characteristics distinguishing plants, animals, and other living things.	2.28	Slightly Difficult
3. Reproductive patterns and life cycles of common organisms.	2.28	Slightly Difficult
4. Factors governing the structures, functions, and behaviors of living systems.	2.72	Moderately Difficult
5. Cycles of matter, and flow of energy, through living and nonliving pathways.	2.78	Moderately Difficult
6. Reproduction and heredity, including human reproduction and contraception.	2.94	Moderately Difficult
7. Structure, function, and reproduction of cells, including microorganisms.	3.11	Moderately Difficult
Mean	2.59	Moderately Difficult

B. Learning Contents in Physical Science

8. Properties of matter such as mass, solubility, and density.	2.89	Moderately Difficult
9. Variations in the physical and chemical states of matter and changes among states.	2.83	Moderately Difficult
10. Factors affecting the position, motion and behavior of objects.	2.89	Moderately Difficult
11. Properties of light, electricity, sound, and magnetism.	3.06	Moderately Difficult
12. Types of energy, energy sources, and simple transformations of energy	2.94	Moderately Difficult
13. States of matter and bonding in relation to molecular behavior and energy	2.94	Moderately Difficult
14. Classifications of elements and compounds.	2.61	Moderately Difficult
Mean	2.88	Moderately Difficult

Learning Content in Earth and Space Science

15. Basic properties of rocks, minerals, water, air, and energy	2.61	Moderately Difficult
16. Causes of the seasons and seasonal changes	2.61	Moderately Difficult
17. Basic properties of rocks, minerals, water, air, and energy.	2.78	Moderately Difficult
18. Earth's structure, evolution, history, and place in the solar system.	3.00	Moderately Difficult
19. Differences between renewable and non-renewable natural resources	2.78	Moderately Difficult

20. Characteristics and importance of oceans, lakes, rivers, and the water cycle.	2.61	Moderately Difficult
Mean	2.73	Moderately Difficult
Overall Mean	2.74	Moderately Difficult

Legend: 3-50 = 4.00 = Extremely Difficult ; 2.50- 3.49 = Moderately Difficult ; 2.50 – 2.49 = Slightly Difficult ; 1.00 - 1.49 = Not Difficult

Difficulties in Methods and Strategies

Table 3 reveals the difficulties in methods in strategies encountered by the teachers in Pangutaran District, MBHTE-Sulu. The overall mean for the difficulties was 2.73 with a verbal description of moderately difficult.

Table 3 : Difficulties in Methods and Strategies

Difficulties	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Engaging students in analyzing and interpreting data and observation	2.67	Moderately Difficult
2. Engaging students in constructing explanations and arguments	2.89	Moderately Difficult
3. Engaging students in using and applying new science concepts in variety of ways and contexts	2.89	Moderately Difficult
4. Engaging students in making connections by synthesizing and summarizing key concepts	2.83	Moderately Difficult
5. Engaging students in communication in scientific ways	2.61	Moderately Difficult
6. Engaging students to answer questions which elicits their ideas and predictions	2.67	Moderately Difficult
7. Engaging students to answer questions that will challenge their thinking	2.67	Moderately Difficult
8. Engaging students to answer questions to probe their ideas and predictions	2.78	Moderately Difficult
9. Engaging students to participate in class experiments and laboratory works	2.83	Moderately Difficult
10. Engaging students to participate in class simulation activities	2.56	Moderately Difficult
11. Engaging students in some practical work activities	2.67	Moderately Difficult
12. Engaging students in field trips	2.89	Moderately Difficult
13. Engaging students in a role play	2.83	Moderately Difficult
14. Engaging students in writing activities	2.72	Moderately Difficult

15. Engaging students to present some group activities outputs 2.50 Moderately Difficult

Overall Mean 2.73 Moderately Difficult

Legend: 3-50 = 4.00 = Extremely Difficult ; 2.50- 3.49 = Moderately Difficult; 2.50 – 2.49 = Slightly Difficult ; 1.00 - 1.49 = Not Difficult

Difficulties in Teaching the Learning Contents and Difficulties in Methods and Strategies According to Gender

Table 4 exposes the significant difference on the difficulties of teaching the learning contents in Science as well as the difficulties in terms of choosing the methods and strategies in teaching the said subject according to gender. The following results were revealed: In terms of teaching the learning contents, the Sig. values is .085 ; and as to methods and strategies, the sig. value is .510.

Table 4: Significant Difference in Terms Difficulties of Teaching the Learning Content and Difficulties in terms of method and strategies According to Gender

	Gender	N	Mean	Sig. Val	Interpretation
Difficulties in Learning Content	Male	5	2.3800	.085	No Significant Difference
	Female	13	2.8731	.	
Difficulties in Methods and Strategies	Male	5	2.5880	.510	No Significant Difference
	Female	13	2.7885		

Difficulties of Teaching the Learning Contents and Methods and Strategies According to Age

Table 5 highlights the significant difference on the difficulties of teaching the learning contents in Science as well as the difficulties in terms of choosing the methods and strategies in teaching the said subject according to Age. The following results were found : In terms of teaching the learning contents, the Sig. values is .649 ; and as to methods and strategies, the sig. value is .598.

Table 5 : Significant Difference on the Difficulties in terms of teaching learning contents in science and difficulties in method and strategies According to Age

		Sum of Squares	F	Sig.	Decision	Interpretation
Difficulties in Learning Content	Between Groups	.562	.562	.649	Ho is Accepted	No Significant Difference
	Within Groups					
Difficulties in Methods and Strategies	Between Groups	.646	.646	.598	Ho is Accepted	No Significant Difference
	Within Groups	.329				

Difficulties of Teaching the Learning Contents and Methods and Strategies According to Educational Qualifications

Table 6 reveals the significant difference on the difficulties of teaching the learning contents in Science as well as the difficulties in terms of choosing the methods and strategies in teaching the said subject according to educational qualification. The following results were found: In terms of teaching the learning contents, the Sig. values is .222 ; and as to methods and strategies, the sig. value is .147.

Table 6: Significant Difference on the Difficulties in terms of teaching learning contents in science and difficulties in method and strategies According to Educational Qualification

		Sum of Squares	F	Sig.	Decision	Interpretation
Difficulties in Learning Content	Between Groups	.918	.222	.222	Ho is Accepted	No Significant Difference
	Within Groups	4.131				
Difficulties in Methods and Strategies	Between Groups	1.183	.147	.147	Ho is Accepted	No Significant Difference
	Within Groups					

Within
Groups 4.067

Difficulties of Teaching the Learning Contents and Methods and Strategies According to Teaching Experience

Table 7 exposes the significant difference on the difficulties of teaching the learning contents in Science as well as the difficulties in terms of choosing the methods and strategies in teaching the said subject according to teaching experiences. The following results were revealed: In terms of teaching the learning contents, the Sig. values is .762 ; and as to methods and strategies, the sig. value is .313.

Table 7: Significant Difference on the Difficulties in terms of teaching learning contents in science and difficulties in method and strategies According to Teaching Experience

		Sum of Squares	F	Sig.	Decision	Interpretation
Difficulties in Learning Content	Between Groups	.390	.762	.762	Ho is Accepted	No Significant Difference
	Within Groups					
	Total	1.303	.313	.313	Ho is Accepted	No Significant Difference
Difficulties in Methods and Strategies	Between Groups	4.104				
	Within Groups					
	Total	5.250				

DISCUSSION

This section discusses the results of the study on the difficulties encountered by the elementary school teachers in Pangutaran District, MBHTE-Sulu in the teaching leaning contents in Science. This Includes the profile of the respondents, the difficulties experienced by the teachers in teaching the learning contents Biology, Physical science and Earth and Space science and difficulties in terms of methods and strategies.

A. Profile of the Respondents

Gleaning from the Table 1, the majority 130 (72.2%) of the elementary school teachers were female and only 50 (45%) were male. This data suggest that the number of female teachers is greater than the male teachers.

In terms of age, majority 90 (50 %) of elementary school teachers of MBHTE-Sulu were belonging to an age bracket of 36-45 years old; while, 49 (27.5%) of them were at 25-35 years old. Meanwhile, 3 (25%) of them were belonging to 46-55 years old. And only 11 (5.9 %) of them were at 56-65 years old. Hence, it can be deduced that most of elementary school teachers of MBHTE-Sulu were at the middle age and still have the passion to teach.

As to their educational qualification, majority 110 (61.1%) have finished their bachelor's degree. While 59 (33.0%) of them were already having their masteral units. Further, only 11 (5.9%) has finished his/her master's degree. And none of the elementary school teachers of the said district have advanced into doctoral studies. This implies, the teachers still need to go on professional advancement so that they can best deliver the basic services expected of them by the pupils and parents. As Radjuni (2021) in his study on Teachers' Profile and Classroom Instruction Delivery: The Case of a Certain University in the Southern Philippines, pointed out that quality teachers are fundamental factor for improving classroom instruction that in turns improve the quality of education.

In terms of teaching experience, majority 80 (44.4%) have already been in service from 5-10 years; while 60 (33.3 %) have below 5 years of teaching experience; and only 40 (22.3%) of them have been serving from 10 years and above.

The findings denote that majority of the elementary school teachers in MBHTE-Sulu still needs to gain more experiences in the service to help them acquaint themselves with the challenges emanates in the teaching profession. Succinctly, Radjuni (2021) in his study on Glocalization an emerging approach in teacher Education, concluded that there is an urgent needs to recognize what the teachers need to do in order to prepare young people for a modern world in today's educational dynamism.

Abdurahman & Omar (2021) corroborates, in their study on School head's leadership practice and teachers' performance : The case of Omar District, Division of Sulu, Philippines, that 73.2% of the elementary school teachers in Sulu are female and 26.8 percent female. This finding is also supported by Abdurahman (2020) in his study on Job satisfaction and performance of the secondary school teachers in the schools' Division of Sulu, Philippines which states that 72% of all teachers are women, 12% are secondary school principals and 10% are superintendents.

B. Difficulties in Teaching the Learning Content in Science

Table 2 exposes the level of difficulties in teaching the learning contents in Science which covers learning content in Biology, Physical Science, and Earth and Space Science. In adherence to the said Table 2 , the over all mean is 2. 74 which has a verbal description of Moderately Difficult. This implies that the elementary school teachers in MBHTE-Sulu have experienced moderate difficulties in teaching the Science contents.

Categorically, the teachers found that teaching the learning content in Biology would be moderately difficult ($m=2.59$). When taking singly, they found teaching the

following contents would be moderately difficult such as: Factors governing the structures, functions, and behaviors of living systems; Cycles of matter, and flow of energy, through living and nonliving pathways; Reproduction and heredity, including human reproduction and contraception; and Structure, function, and reproduction of cells, including microorganisms. However, they also found the following contents to be slightly difficult such as: Features distinguishing living from non-living systems; Characteristics distinguishing plants, animals, and other living things; and Reproductive patterns and life cycles of common organisms.

In the area of Physical Science (mean = 2.88) , the teachers found that teaching the learning contents of the said subject to be moderately difficult, Specifically the following: Properties of matter such as mass, solubility, and density; Variations in the physical and chemical states of matter and changes among states; Factors affecting the position, motion and behavior of objects; Properties of light, electricity, sound, and magnetism ; Types of energy, energy sources, and simple transformations of energy; States of matter and bonding in relation to molecular behavior and energy; and Classifications of elements and compounds.

Similarly, the teachers also found that teaching the learning content in Earth and Space Science (m= 2.73) would be moderately difficult, to wit: Basic properties of rocks, minerals, water, air, and energy ; Causes of the seasons and seasonal changes ; Basic properties of rocks, minerals, water, air, and energy ; Earth's structure, evolution, history, and place in the solar system ; Differences between renewable and non-renewable natural resources ; and Characteristics and importance of oceans, lakes, rivers, and the water cycle.

Corollary to this finding, Chavan (2013) found out that most of the teachers have difficulties in understanding biology concepts like Alkali, base & oxides, Photosynthesis, sexual reproduction and even drawing diagrams in the board. In earth science, they also found difficulties in teaching the concept of earth quakes, tsunami and even water movements. In the same vein, Chakour R., Alami A., Selmaoul S. & Zaki M (2019) have likewise revealed that the major difficulties that hinder the teaching of natural science are mainly related to their field of specialization where most teachers who taught the subject were specializing in Biology during their university studies.

Finally, the finding is reinforced by Al-Momani (2017) in a different perspective. He found out that the difficulties facing the science teachers include administrative and organizational skills, personal and ethical domain, educational skills and specialized scientific literacy.

C. Difficulties in Methods and Strategies

As revealed in Table 3, The teachers found out that choosing appropriate methods and strategies would be moderately difficult as manifested by an overall mean of 2.73.

Accordingly, the teachers found the following to moderately difficult such as : Engaging students in analyzing and interpreting the data and observation; Engaging them in constructing explanations and arguments; Engaging them in using and applying new science concepts in variety of ways and contexts; Engaging them in making connections by synthesizing and summarizing key concepts; and Engaging them in communication in scientific ways. Further, they also found the following to be moderately difficult like; Engaging them to answer questions which elicits their ideas and predictions; Engaging them to answer questions that will challenge their thinking; to answer questions to probe their ideas and predictions; and Engaging them to participate in class experiments and laboratory works; and Engaging students to participate in class simulation activities. Moreover, they likewise found the following to be moderately difficult such that Engaging students in some practical work activities; Engaging them in field trips, in role play, in writing activities, and engaging them to present some group activity outputs.

In this regard, Henderson and Wellington (2016, p39) suggest the teachers should explore 'different ways of getting students to present written records of investigations and observations and to give them the opportunity of showing that they understand a scientific topic or concept'. For this reason, recently, such form of writing a journals, questions, cartoons, and brief narrative have gained popularity as a means of helping students to understand the scientific material (Prain and Hand, 2016; hand, Prain Lawrence and Yore, 2016).

Many different methods and strategies have been suggested for involving students in lessons and engaging them in active learning (Trowbridge et al 2018; Deboer, 2018; Goodrum et al 2018). However, in order for any method to be successful, effective lesson planning is essential (Henson and Eller, 2016; Harlen, 2016). A lesson plan requires teachers to be clear about the sequence of the activities in the lessons, the purpose and goals of the lessons. The planning process involves clarification of the roles of the teacher and students. Thus, it makes easier for students to follow the teacher's material and encourages them to participate more in the lesson and take responsibility for their own learning (Good and Brophy, 2016; Calderon et al, 2016). For these reasons, effective lesson planning has a positive effective on students' learning (Brown, 2016; Tomic 2016; Glenn, 2018).

Moreover, according to the above, teachers should allow some flexibility in lesson planning in order to encourage students to participate more in the lessons. It is important to be sensitive to the mood of the class and if something is not going to well to abandon it and move on or change tack completely. Otherwise, a rigid lesson plan potentially hinders rather than helps the teaching-learning process, since it could prevent students from being involved in the lessons and reduce their creativity.

D. Difficulties in Teaching the Learning Contents and Difficulties in Methods and Strategies According to Gender

Gleaning from Table 4, there could be no significant difference found between the perception of the male and female teachers of MBHTE-Sulu in terms of difficulties in

teaching the learning contents in Science as attested by the Sig. value of .085 which is above the 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the hypothesis which states “ that there is no significant difference on the perception of male and female teachers in terms of difficulties in teaching the learning contents in Science” was hereby accepted.

Similarly, there could be no significant difference found between the perceptions of the male and female teachers of MBHTE-Sulu in terms of difficulties in choosing the method and strategies in teaching Science as attested by the Sig. value of 0.510 which is above the 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the hypothesis which states “ that there is no significant difference on the perception of male and female teachers in terms of difficulties in choosing the method and strategies in teaching Science” was hereby accepted. This implies that the perception of male and female teachers in terms of difficulties in teaching the learning contents in Science and in terms of the difficulties in choosing the methods and strategies in teaching the subject do not vary significantly.

Contrary to this finding, Osborne, Simon, & Collins (2003) found that gender differences have always been manifested in student performance in the classroom. Hence, even though, there is no significant difference in matters of difficulties in teaching the science content between male and female teachers, the learning performance of the students in the classroom still vary significantly.

E. Difficulties in Teaching the Learning Contents and Difficulties in Methods and Strategies According to Age

As found in Table 5, There was no significant difference found on the perception of teachers of MBHTE-Sulu across all age groups as to the difficulties in teaching the learning contents in Science as attested by the Sig. value of 0.649 which is above the 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the hypothesis which states “ that there is no significant difference on the perception of teachers in MBHTE-Sulu as to difficulties in teaching the learning contents in Science” according to age was hereby accepted. This means that regardless of age of teachers, their perceptions were almost the same.

Similarly, there could be no significant difference on the perception of teachers of MBHTE-Sulu in terms of difficulties in choosing the appropriate method and strategies in teaching Science as to their age. This was attested by the Sig. value of 0.598 which is above the 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the hypothesis which states “ that there is no significant difference on the perceptions of teachers in terms of difficulties in method and strategies in teaching Science” was hereby accepted. This implies that , regardless of age, the perception of teachers in terms of difficulties in methods and strategies in teaching the subject do not vary significantly.

F. Difficulties in Teaching the Learning Contents and Difficulties in Methods and Strategies According to Educational Qualification

Based from Table 6, There was no significant difference found on the perception of teachers of MBHTE-Sulu as to the difficulties in teaching the learning contents in

Science according to their educational qualification. This is manifested by the Sig. value of 0.222 which is above the 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the hypothesis which states “ that there is no significant difference on the perception of teachers in MBHTE-Sulu as to difficulties in teaching the learning contents in Science according to their educational qualification” was hereby accepted. This means that regardless of educational qualifications of teachers, their perceptions were almost the same.

Also, there was no significant difference on the perception of teachers of MBHTE-Sulu in terms of difficulties in choosing the method and strategies in teaching Science as to their educational qualification. This was attested by the Sig. value of 0.147 which is above the 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the hypothesis which states “ that there is no significant difference on the perception of teachers in terms of difficulties in choosing the method and strategies in teaching Science as to their educational qualification” was hereby accepted. This implies that , regardless of educational qualification, the perception of teachers in terms of difficulties in methods and strategies in teaching the subject do not vary significantly.

G. Difficulties in Teaching the Learning Contents and Difficulties in Methods and Strategies According to Length of Service

As revealed in Table 7, There was no significant difference found on the perception of teachers of MBHTE-Sulu as to the difficulties in teaching the learning contents in Science according to their teaching experience. This is attested by the Sig. value of 0.762 which is above the 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the hypothesis which states “ that there is no significant difference on the perception of teachers in MBHTE-Sulu as to difficulties in teaching the learning contents in Science according to their teaching experiences “was hereby accepted. This means that both new and old teachers of MBHTE-Sulu had almost shared the same perceptions in terms of difficulties they encountered.

likewise, there was no significant difference on the perception of teachers of MBHTE-Sulu in terms of difficulties in choosing the method and strategies in teaching Science as to their educational qualification. This was attested by the Sig. value of 0.313 which is above the 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the hypothesis which states “ that there is no significant difference on the perception of teachers in terms of difficulties in choosing the method and strategies in teaching Science as to their teaching experiences” was hereby accepted. This implies that , the perception of teachers ,regardless of teaching experiences, in terms of difficulties in methods and strategies in teaching the subject do not vary significantly.

Conclusions

On the basis of the findings of the study, the following conclusions are hereby drawn: That majority of the elementary school teachers in Pangutaran District were female, belonging to 36-45 years of age ; with bachelors’; and with 5-10 years teaching experience; That teaching the learning contents in Science in areas of Biology ; That learning contents in Physical Science; and Life and Space Science were found to be

moderately difficult; That selecting the appropriate method in teaching science were also found to be moderately difficult. That There was no significant difference found on the difficulties of teaching the learning contents in science in the areas of Biology, Physical Science and Life and Space Science According to Respondents' Profile. Hence, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference on the difficulties in teaching Science according respondents' profile" was accepted; And that there was no significant difference found on the difficulties in terms of methods and strategies according to Respondents' Profile. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference on the difficulties in teaching Science according respondents' profile" was accepted.

Recommendations:

1. MBHTE-BARMM may use the findings of this study as basis for continuing professional development program of teachers cascading to the different divisions of the Bangsamoro Autonomous Regions in an effort to produce quality education standard.
2. School Division Superintendent may also use the result of this study as basis for the administration of Division Assessment Test in Science to find out some affecting the teaching and learning of the same subject.
3. School administrators may institutionalize training programs for science faculty members to help improve classroom performance.
4. Teachers must also institutionalize some intervention programs to help maximize pupils' motivation and academic achievements especially in science.
5. School supervisor must also craft a development agenda by having a school-based pedagogical training in Science in the entire district or division as a whole.

Ethical Considerations

This study prioritizes the ethical treatment of all participants, specifically MBHTE-Sulu division teachers. The researchers always aimed to safeguard the right to privacy of the respondents while exploring crucial topic as fellow academicians.

Foremost, a detailed informed consent form was provided to the respondents that clearly explains the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks and benefits, and as well as how confidentiality is maintained. Teachers were also informed that their participation is entirely voluntary and they have the right to withdraw at any point in time without any repercussions. Furthermore, anonymization of all data collected from the study was strictly observed where no particular information of the respondents was linked to the same. In respect to the privacy of the participants, data collection occurred in a private setting and said data were stored in a secured archive where only the researchers themselves can accessed. Likewise, all participants were treated with respect regardless of their dissenting views and opinions. Moreover, the researchers had strived to create a safe and comfortable space for the respondents in order to give them the leeway to share their experiences.

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